

Intra- and inter-hemispheric functional connectivity: a Graph Neural Network study as a transdiagnosis approach for psychopathological underpinnings

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Abstract

Inter-hemispheric functional connectivity (ihFC) is altered across a range of psychopathological conditions and reorganises substantially during childhood and adolescence. Their respective contributions to transdiagnostic dimension of psychopathology in youth are not often examined within a single model. The present study addressed this gap by training graph neural networks (GNNs) on whole-brain resting-state functional connectivity from the Philadelphia Neurodevelopmental Cohort (N = 1,308) to predict seven dimensions of psychopathology, and by using edge-class ablations to isolate the contribution of inter- and intra-hemispheric edges to each prediction. Predictive accuracy was concentrated in the psychosis-spectrum dimensions, namely psychosis, depression, and obsession/compulsion, while attention, anxiety, bipolarity, and conduct were not reliably predicted, a ranking consistent with prior multivariate findings in the same cohort. Edge-class ablations dissociated the two connectivity types. Removing intra-hemispheric edges produced consistent, anatomically specific degradation across the three psychosis-spectrum dimensions, whereas removing inter-hemispheric edges yielded effects valenced with respect to symptom severity, degrading predictions for high-scoring participants and improving them for low-scoring participants. Age further modulated this organisation, with older participants relying more on intra-hemispheric and less on inter-hemispheric edges, consistent with the broader developmental shift from distributed to local cortical processing. These results indicate that brain-behaviour associations in youth are structured by symptom dimension, severity, and developmental stage, rather than constituting a single uniform connectivity signature.

Keywords: brain, function-behavior, rs-fMRI, transdiagnostic, GNNs

1. Introduction

Inter-hemispheric functional connectivity (ihFC), defined as the temporal correlation of neural activity between regions in the right and left cerebral hemisphere, is a fundamental feature of the human brain. Disruptions in this connectivity have been documented across a range of psychopathological conditions, with alterations observed as early as childhood or adolescence across different psychopathological conditions, including in schizophrenia (Li et al. 2015; Chang et al. 2019), major depressive disorder (Jiang et al. 2025; Hagen et al. 2025), autism spectrum disorder (Yao et al. 2021; Wan et al. 2023) and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (Tarchi et al. 2022; Yao and Kendrick 2022). For instance, youth onset schizophrenia is frequently characterized by a marked reduction in inter-hemispheric coordination within the prefrontal and primary sensory cortices, a deficit strongly associated with the emergence of positive symptoms and cognitive decline (Li et al. 2015). In contrast, major depressive disorder during adolescence has been associated with increased inter-hemispheric connectivity within the affective network, specifically between the bilateral amygdala, suggesting that a loss of hemispheric specialization in emotional processing may serve as a critical biomarker for early onset mood dysregulation (Jiang et al. 2025). Across these conditions, ihFC disruptions emerge predominantly during childhood and adolescence, a period during which homotopic functional connectivity is itself still maturing. ihFC undergoes systematic change across this developmental window, declining with age across multiple resting-state networks in a pattern specific to youth (Tarchi et al. 2022; Tarchi et al. 2023). Alterations of ihFC in the context of psychopathological condition may reflect deviations from this ongoing maturational process rather than a fixed dysconnectivity pattern, highlighting the importance of studying these alterations within a neurodevelopmental framework.

With evidence that ihFC is altered across psychopathological conditions, these connectivity patterns likely reflect shared transdiagnostic variation in psychological functioning. Identifying these shared neural substrates is critical for establishing ihFC as a viable biomarker and for understanding the mechanisms that shape individual differences in psychological functioning, improving early identification and guiding the development of targeted interventions. Given the complexity and heterogeneity of psychopathological conditions, identifying shared mechanisms across different diagnostic categories has become a major research focus. Transdiagnostic and multimodal approaches in developmental cohorts have shown promise for uncovering these underlying processes (Parkes, Satterthwaite, and Bassett 2020). Treating psychopathology as a continuum rather than a set of discrete categories enables a more precise characterization of how psychiatric conditions manifest across individuals.

Interpreting ihFC alterations requires situating them against intra-hemispheric connectivity, which serves a complementary and functionally distinct role. The two forms of connectivity are often dissociable. In schizophrenia, for instance, patients show marked inter-hemispheric hypoconnectivity across hub regions while intra-hemispheric network topology remains largely preserved (Zhang et al. 2019). This dissociation means that, without a within-hemisphere reference, it is unclear whether reported ihFC alterations reflect a specifically inter-hemispheric disturbance or a more general connectivity disruption that happens to manifest across hemispheres. Several studies have examined one form of connectivity in isolation, or restrict inter-hemispheric analyses to homotopic region pairs (Yao and Kendrick 2022; Zhao et al. 2017). As a result, the broader inter-hemispheric signal and its specificity relative to intra-hemispheric connectivity remain poorly characterized across psychopathological dimensions, and across the developmental window during

which these alterations first emerge. Characterizing these shared neural patterns, and separating the contribution of inter- from intra-hemispheric connectivity, requires a model that represents both at once. Standard approaches often reduce the functional connectivity to a list of independent features, or restrict inter-hemispheric comparisons to homotopic pairs, stripping away topological properties such as small-world organisation and modular hierarchy that characterise healthy neural integration. Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) operate directly on graph-structured data: regions are treated as nodes and functional correlations as weighted edges, so each connection is interpreted in the context of the wider network rather than on its own (Li et al. 2021; Bessadok, Mahjoub, and Rekik 2023). This preserves the structural context of the connectome and allows non-linear interactions between inter- and intra-hemispheric signaling to be captured within a single model. To isolate the contribution of each connectivity type, ablation can be applied directly to the GNN’s input graph, selectively suppressing inter- or intra-hemispheric edges and quantifying the resulting change in predictive accuracy. This follows the rationale of perturbation-based GNN interpretability methods [GNNExplainer (Ying et al. 2019); GraphMask (Xu et al. 2024)], adapted here to a hypothesis-driven contrast between anatomically defined edge sets rather than data-driven mask learning. This makes it possible to move beyond a global account of dysconnectivity and identify which spatial pathways drive the relationship between functional connectivity and psychopathological symptoms.

The present study aims to characterize how inter- and intrahemispheric functional connectivity relates to psychopathological dimensions, using data from the Philadelphia Neurodevelopmental Cohort (PNC; $N = 1,308$), a large-scale neurodevelopmental dataset (Satterthwaite et al. 2014; Satterthwaite et al. 2016). Adopting a transdiagnostic, data-driven framework, we trained a GNN on whole-brain functional connectivity matrices to predict individual differences in psychopathological dimensions, with separate ablation analyses examining the contributions of inter- and intra-hemispheric connectivity.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Participants

Multi-modal data were obtained from the publicly available Philadelphia Neurodevelopmental Cohort (PNC) (Satterthwaite et al. 2016), a large-scale neurodevelopmental dataset. The cohort comprised 1,343 participants between 8 and 21 years of age, all of whom completed a comprehensive battery of assessments, including multimodal MRI (diffusion-weighted, structural, task-based, and resting-state functional imaging), cognitive and psychological evaluations, and whole-genome genotyping from blood samples. For the present study, we focused on psychopathological measures and resting-state functional MRI data. Participants were excluded from the analysis due to missing data ($n=2$), excessive motion ($n=164$), or incomplete psychological records ($n=29$). Participants whose psychopathological and MRI assessments were separated by more than six months were also excluded ($n=262$). After applying these criteria, the final sample comprised 886 participants (477 females; mean age = 15.2 ± 3.3 years).

2.2. Psychopathological data and factor analysis

Psychopathological measures were collected via the GOASSESS, a modified structured clinical interview covering mood, anxiety, behavioral, eating disorders, psychosis spectrum symptoms, and substance use (Calkins et al. 2014). Remaining missing values in psychopathological participants' measures were addressed through multiple imputation by chained equations (MICE). Following recommendation from previous study (Cropley et al. 2021), factor analysis performed on those scores identified seven independent components representing continuous dimensions of psychopathological symptoms, including *psychosis*, *attention*, *depression*, *anxiety*, *bipolarity*, symptoms related to *conduct* and *obsessive-compulsive disorders*. Factor analysis was performed exclusively on participants included in the graph-based predictive model to avoid data leakage, serving exclusively to operationalize the outcome variables.

2.3. Magnetic Resonance Imaging Data

Anatomical T1-weighted (T1w) image (MPRAGE, TR=1810ms, TE=3.5ms, voxel size =) and resting-state fMRI (rs-fMRI) images (TR = 3000 ms, TE = 32 ms, voxel size = $3 \times 3 \times 3$ mm, acquisition time = 6 min) were preprocessed using fMRIPrep (Esteban et al. 2019), ensuring standardized processing methods. Anatomical preprocessing included intensity non-uniformity correction, skull stripping, brain tissue segmentation, and cortical surface reconstruction using FreeSurfer 7.3.2, followed by nonlinear spatial normalization to the MNI152NLin2009cAsym standard template via ANTs. For functional data, preprocessing included head-motion correction using MCFLIRT, slice-time correction, and co-registration of the BOLD reference to the T1w image using boundary-based registration. Confound estimation included framewise displacement (FD), DVARS, global signals (CSF, white matter, and whole brain), and physiological noise components derived from both temporal and anatomical CompCor decompositions. Frames exceeding 0.5 mm FD or 1.5 standardized DVARS were flagged as motion outliers (Power et al. 2014). BOLD time-series were ultimately resampled into MNI152NLin2009cAsym standard space using a single-interpolation-step approach combining all relevant transformations. All preprocessed data were visually inspected using the quality reports generated by fMRIPrep prior to further analysis.

Functional connectivity (FC) matrices were computed using the homotopic Markov Random Field (hMRF) 400 atlas (Yan et al. 2023), with pairwise connectivity strength estimated via Pearson's correlation using Nilearn v0.12.1.

2.4. Graph Neural Network (GNN) architecture, training, and evaluation

To model associations between FC and psychopathological factors, a GNN was trained using individual FC matrices as inputs and the seven factor scores as simultaneous prediction targets. Each participant’s FC matrix was modeled as a graph, where nodes represented brain regions of interest (ROIs) and edges represented pairwise connectivity strength. To focus on the most robust connections while ensuring a fully connected graph, proportional thresholding was tested at 3 different densities (0.01, 0.1, and 0.2). The GNN was implemented as a multi-output regression model with all outcomes equally weighted in a MSE loss function. Two architectures were evaluated, ARMA and GCN, within a common framework supporting configurable hidden channel dimensionality (16, 32, 64, 128, or 256), network depth (2, 3, 4, or 6 layers), dropout rate (0.0, 0.2, or 0.3), normalization type (LayerNorm or BatchNorm), jumping knowledge aggregation strategy (max, last, or concatenation), and optional residual connections. Both standard and edge-weight-aware message passing modes were evaluated, and the final graph-level representation was passed through a linear regression head to produce continuous factor score predictions. Subjects were partitioned into a training and validation set ($N = 614$ (323 female, 15.3 ± 3.2 years), 70%) and a held-out test set ($N = 264$ (154 female, 15.1 ± 3.4 years), 30%). Within the training set, a 10-fold cross-validation scheme was applied, with 85% of subjects used for fitting and 15% for validation in each fold; splits were pre-computed and held fixed across all model configurations to ensure identical data partitions. For each fold, a model was initialized from scratch and trained using the Adam optimizer with configurable learning rate (0.0001 or 0.001) and weight decay (0.0 or 0.001) for up to 300 epochs, with early stopping based on validation loss (patience = 35 epochs). Batch sizes of 16, 32, and 64 were tested. Performance was evaluated using R^2 , MAE, MSE, and RMSE, computed per outcome variable and aggregated across folds (mean \pm SD). Hyperparameter optimization was conducted via a Bayesian search using Weights & Biases (wandb), minimizing mean validation loss across folds within a 48-hour time limit. To ensure full reproducibility, all random number generators were seeded with a fixed value (seed = 42) and CUDA operations were set to deterministic mode.

2.5. Post-hoc edge ablation

To assess the contribution of specific FC networks to model predictions without retraining, we performed a post-hoc ablation analysis on the held-out test set using the best-performing model, selected as the model with the highest mean R^2 across the seven factors, averaged over cross-validation folds.

Spatial specificity was probed at two complementary levels using the Yeo decomposition of the hMRF atlas (Yan et al. 2023), which assigns each of the 400 parcels to the left or right hemisphere. At the whole-brain hemispheric level, two ablations were defined: removal of all inter-hemispheric edges (connecting left- to right-hemisphere nodes) and removal of all intra-hemispheric edges (both endpoints in the same hemisphere).

We evaluated edge ablations on three questions using different statistical approaches described in details below: (i) whether the ablated edges carry more predictive information than a random subset of equivalent size (group-level: Permutation test for edge specificity and subject-level: Wilcoxon signed-rank test against baseline) (ii) whether ablation degrades predictions consistently across individuals (paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test on per-subject residuals) and (iii) whether susceptibility to ablation varies with target factor score, age, or sex (subject-level: factor score–ablation susceptibility correlation; and subject-level: Sex and age associations). Of note,

age referred to the age at scan, and sex referred to participant-reported biological sex.

Group-level: Permutation test for edge specificity To assess whether the anatomical identity of the removed edges contained predictive information beyond what would be expected from their count alone, we performed a Monte Carlo permutation test. For each ablation condition and factor, $n_{\text{perms}} = 1000$ null R^2 values were generated by removing the same number of edges as the target ablation, drawn uniformly at random without replacement from the upper triangle of the connectivity matrix. Each random mask was applied identically to all subjects in the test set, and inference was run with the trained model to obtain a null R^2 . The one-sided empirical p -value was computed as

$$p = \frac{\#\{R_{\text{perm},k}^2 \leq R_{\text{abl}}^2\} + 1}{n_{\text{perms}} + 1}, \quad (1)$$

The test is one-sided because of the directional hypothesis asking whether the specific edges are more damaging than random edges, not whether they differ in either direction. The minimum achievable p -value is $1/1001 \approx 0.001$. Note that this test does not assess whether the absolute R^2 drop from baseline is statistically significant; it assesses only whether the removed edges carry more information than an equivalent random subset.

Subject-level: Wilcoxon signed-rank test against baseline (vs-baseline) To assess whether ablation produced a consistent, directional degradation of predictions at the subject-level, we applied a one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test to the per-subject absolute residuals. For each subject i , condition, and factor, the absolute residual under ablation, $|r_i^{\text{abl}}|$, was paired with the absolute residual under the full baseline model, $|r_i^{\text{base}}|$, yielding paired differences across all $N = 264$ subjects. The test evaluates whether the median subject experiences an increase in prediction error following ablation. Unlike the aggregate permutation test, this analysis captures the consistency of the effect across individuals: a non-significant result can occur even when aggregate R^2 drops substantially, if the ablation hurts some subjects and helps others in approximately equal measure.

Subject-level: Wilcoxon signed-rank test against permutation mean (vs-permutation) A second one-sided Wilcoxon signed-rank test was applied at the subject level to assess specificity. For each subject i , we paired the absolute residual under the target ablation, $|r_i^{\text{abl}}|$, with the mean absolute residual computed across the $n_{\text{perms}} = 1,000$ permutation runs, $|r_i^{\text{perm}}| = \frac{1}{n_{\text{perms}}} \sum_{k=1}^{n_{\text{perms}}} |r_{i,k}^{\text{perm}}|$. The test evaluates whether removing the specific anatomical edges harms a given subject more than removing an equivalent number of randomly chosen edges would on average.

Subject-level: factor score–ablation susceptibility correlation To characterise the relationship between a subject’s factor score and their susceptibility to ablation, Pearson correlations were computed between each subject’s factor score (the target value) and their per-subject $\Delta|r| = |r_i^{\text{abl}}| - |r_i^{\text{baseline}}|$. A positive correlation indicates that subjects with higher factor scores are more harmed by the ablation; a negative correlation indicates a reversal pattern in which high-scoring subjects are helped while low-scoring subjects are hurt. The same correlation was computed using the permutation-mean $\Delta|r|$ to characterise the expected slope under random edge removal, providing a visual and quantitative reference for the specificity of the target ablation slope.

Figure 1: Data from the Philadelphia Neurodevelopmental Cohort ($N = 886$, ages 8–21) included resting state fMRI and psychopathological assessments. Psychopathological data were factor-analyzed into seven dimensions. rs-fMRI was preprocessed with fMRIPrep, and functional connectivity matrices were computed at whole-brain and at hemispheric levels. Graph neural networks predicted psychopathological dimensions from connectivity patterns, with edge-focused ablations and null models used to identify key connections.

Subject-level: Age and sex To examine whether ablation effects were modulated by demographic variables, Pearson correlations between $\Delta|r|$ and age were computed for each condition \times factor combination, and Mann–Whitney U tests were used to compare $\Delta|r|$ between male and female subjects.

3. Results

3.1. Graph Neural Network performance

Following 10-fold cross-validation across hyperparameter configurations, the ARMA architecture achieved the strongest predictive performance. The optimal configuration consisted of 3 layers, a hidden dimension of 64, a dropout rate of 0.2, a learning rate of $1e-4$, and an edge-weight sparsification threshold retaining the top 10% of connections. Table 1 reports performance across all target dimensions.

Table 1: Prediction performance (Mean \pm SD) across 10-fold cross-validation of the best model..

Factor	Cross-validation set			Test set
	R ²	MAE	RMSE	Test R ²
Psychosis	0.154 \pm 0.10	0.718 \pm 0.05	0.929 \pm 0.06	0.25
Attention	0.023 \pm 0.02	0.771 \pm 0.01	1.027 \pm 0.01	0.06
Depression	0.077 \pm 0.06	0.755 \pm 0.03	1.09 \pm 0.04	0.18
Anxiety	0.058 \pm 0.05	0.74 \pm 0.02	0.99 \pm 0.03	0.05
Bipolarity	-0.01 \pm 0.01	0.724 \pm 0.01	0.974 \pm 0.01	-0.04
Conduct	0.003 \pm 0.01	0.74 \pm 0.01	0.98 \pm 0.01	-0.04
Obsession/compulsion	0.105 \pm 0.07	0.71 \pm 0.03	0.91 \pm 0.04	0.18

After selecting this configuration, we retrained the model on the full training set and evaluated it on the held-out test set. The model achieved $R^2 = 0.25$ for *psychosis*, 0.18 for both *depression* and *obsession/compulsion*, and 0.06 for *attention* and *anxiety*, while performance on *bipolarity* and *conduct* was near zero or negative. These results indicate that *psychosis*, *depression*, and *obsession/compulsion* are the most reliably predicted targets, while *attention* and *anxiety* show only a weak effect. *Bipolarity* and *conduct* could not be predicted from the data and we therefore do not report their performances in the ablation in further analysis: identifying informative edges presupposes that the model has learned something worth probing

3.2. Post-hoc edge ablation

For clarity, we present the results separately for inter- and intra-hemispheric ablations, both follow the same analytical pipeline described in the Methods 2.5 section.

Inter-hemispheric ablation. At the group-level, removing inter-hemispheric edges reduced mean R^2 from 0.091 to 0.058 ($\Delta R^2_{\text{base-abl}} = -0.033$, $p = 0.003$). The largest factor-level drops were for *psychosis* ($\Delta R^2_{\text{base-abl}} = 0.092$, $p = 0.002$), *obsession/compulsion* ($\Delta R^2_{\text{base-abl}} = 0.061$, $p = 0.002$), and *anxiety* ($\Delta R^2_{\text{base-abl}} = 0.055$, $p = 0.004$), all significantly exceeding the random-removal baseline. *Attention* ($p = 0.455$) and *depression* ($p = 0.880$) were not significantly affected (see Table 2).

The subject-level picture, however, diverged sharply from the group-level one. The vs-baseline Wilcoxon test showed consistent degradation only for *attention* ($\Delta R^2 = -0.016$, $p = 0.003$) and *depression* ($\Delta R^2 = -0.015$, $p = 0.012$), the two factors with the smallest R at a group-level drops. Conversely, the three factors with the largest drops (*psychosis*, *anxiety*, *obsession/compulsion*) were all non-significant by the Wilcoxon test ($p = 0.320$, 0.352 , and 0.318 , respectively), indicating that their group-level R^2 losses were driven by opposing effects across individuals rather than uniform degradation.

Table 2: Post-hoc edge ablation results: ablated R^2 (R_{abl}^2) vs. permutation R^2 (R_{perm}^2), per condition and factor. z is the z-score against the permutation null; p_{FDR} is the one-sided permutation p -value corrected with Benjamini–Hochberg. Asterisks: $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$, $***p < 0.001$.

Condition	Factor	R_{abl}^2	R_{perm}^2	z	p_{FDR}
Inter-hemispheric ablation	Psychosis	0.159	0.233	−4.64	0.002**
	Attention	0.045	0.046	−0.11	0.455
	Depression	0.167	0.151	1.15	0.880
	Anxiety	−0.002	0.075	−3.80	0.004**
	Obsession/compulsion	0.115	0.168	−3.83	0.002**
	<i>Mean</i>	0.058	0.090	−3.82	0.003**
Intra-hemispheric ablation	Psychosis	0.166	0.233	−4.31	0.002**
	Attention	0.025	0.046	−4.74	0.002**
	Depression	0.067	0.151	−5.82	0.002**
	Anxiety	0.059	0.075	−0.80	0.185
	Obsession/compulsion	0.102	0.168	−4.89	0.002**
	<i>Mean</i>	0.045	0.090	−5.40	0.001***

The vs-permutation Wilcoxon test mirrored this pattern: only *attention* and *depression* showed significant specificity ($p = 0.003$ and $p = 0.017$), while *psychosis*, *anxiety*, and *obsession/compulsion* all yielded non-significant results ($p = 0.647$, 0.148 , and 0.500). For *psychosis* in particular, the combination of a substantial aggregate drop and non-significant subject-level tests reflects the fundamental insensitivity of median-based tests to a reversal pattern: because high-scoring subjects are helped and low-scoring subjects are hurt in approximately equal numbers, the median paired difference is near zero regardless of whether the removal is anatomically specific or random.

Intra-hemispheric ablation. Removing intra-hemispheric edges produced a larger R reduction (mean $R^2 = 0.045$, $\Delta R^2 = -0.046$, $p = 0.001$) and affected a broader set of factors. Significant drops were observed for *psychosis* ($\Delta R^2 = 0.085$, $p = 0.002$), *depression* ($\Delta R^2 = 0.115$, $p = 0.002$), *obsession/compulsion* ($\Delta R^2 = 0.074$, $p = 0.001$), and *attention* ($\Delta R^2 = 0.021$, $p = 0.002$); only *anxiety* was unaffected beyond chance ($p = 0.185$) (see Table 2).

The subject-level tests largely confirmed the findings but with one informative dissociation. The vs-baseline Wilcoxon test showed consistent degradation for *psychosis* ($\Delta R^2 = -0.086$, $p = 9.1 \times 10^{-6}$), *obsession/compulsion* ($\Delta R^2 = -0.074$, $p = 0.001$), and *depression* ($\Delta R^2 = -0.115$, $p = 0.049$, though this was the weakest evidence despite the largest drop). *Attention* showed no consistent subject-level effect ($\Delta R^2 = -0.036$, $p = 0.877$) despite its significant overall R drop, suggesting a heterogeneous pattern in which some subjects were hurt and others helped in approximately equal numbers.

The vs-permutation Wilcoxon test confirmed anatomical specificity for the same three factors that showed consistent degradation: *psychosis* was the clearest case ($p = 1.7 \times 10^{-6}$), followed by *obsession/compulsion* ($p = 0.001$), with *depression* marginal ($p = 0.084$). A notable dissociation emerged for *anxiety*: the vs-baseline test was non-significant ($p = 0.113$), yet the vs-permutation test reached significance ($p = 0.023$). This indicates that the specific intra-hemispheric edges removed for *anxiety* are anatomically privileged — they produce effects that differ from random

Subject-level ablation effect on prediction error: tested vs. baseline and vs. permutation

Figure 2: Subject-level prediction error change following hemispheric edge ablation, tested against baseline and random permutation. Each panel shows the change in absolute residual ($\Delta|r_i| = |r_i^{abl}| - |r_i^{baseline}|$) for individual subjects (dots) as a function of their factor score, separately for inter-hemispheric (top row) and intra-hemispheric (bottom row) edge ablation across the selected five psychopathology dimensions. Red dots indicate subjects for whom ablation increased prediction error (hurt), blue dots indicate subjects for whom ablation decreased prediction error (helped). The solid black line shows the specific ablation regression, the dashed grey line shows the mean regression across 1000 random edge removals of the same size (permutation baseline). Panels background represent the vs-baseline results, the grey one represents when the tests were not significant when the ablated condition was compared directly to the no-ablation baseline (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $p \geq 0.05$); white panels survived that test. The annotated p-value reflects whether the target ablation effect is significantly more extreme than the permutation distribution (one-sided permutation test).

Age modulation of ablation-induced prediction error change (Holm-corrected)

Figure 3: Age modulation of ablation-induced change in prediction error across psychopathology dimensions. Each panel shows the per-subject change in absolute residual ($\Delta|r_i| = |r_i^{abl}| - |r_i^{base}|$) as a function of age, separately for inter-hemispheric (top row) and intra-hemispheric (bottom row) edge ablation across five psychopathology factors. Each grey dot represents one subject. The regression line is shown in red when the Pearson correlation survives Holm–Bonferroni correction across the five factors within each condition (annotated r -value in red), and in dark grey otherwise. A negative slope indicates that older subjects show a smaller ablation-induced error change — i.e., ablating those edges has less impact on their predictions — while a positive slope indicates the opposite.

removal — but those effects are not consistently directional across subjects in a way the median can capture. *Attention* remained non-significant on the vs-permutation test as well ($p = 0.943$), confirming that its overall R drop reflects neither subject-level consistency nor anatomical specificity.

Age and sex association Age modulated ablation effects significantly and in opposite directions for inter- and intra-hemispheric conditions. For inter-hemispheric ablation, Pearson correlations between $\Delta|r|$ and age were negative for five of the seven factors, reaching significance after Holm–Bonferroni correction (across seven factors within the condition) for all studied psychopathological factors (*psychosis* $r = -0.28$, *attention* $r = -0.24$, *depression* $r = -0.44$, *anxiety* $r = -0.26$, and *obsession/compulsion* $r = -0.19$ respectively; all corrected $p < 0.01$). This indicates that older subjects were less harmed by removal of inter-hemispheric edges: the degradation in prediction accuracy from inter-hemispheric ablation diminished with age. For intra-hemispheric ablation, the direction reversed for the same set of factors: correlations were positive and significant for all factors as well (*psychosis* $r = +0.34$, *attention* $r = +0.19$, *depression* $r = +0.37$, *anxiety* $r = +0.21$, and *obsession/compulsion* $r = +0.24$ respectively; all corrected $p < 0.01$), indicating that older subjects were more harmed when intra-hemispheric connections were removed. All results are presented in Figure 3.

Sex did not significantly modulate ablation effects under either condition after Holm–Bonferroni correction. The largest raw difference was observed for inter-hemispheric ablation of depression, where male subjects showed a slightly greater mean increase in absolute residual than female subjects ($\Delta|r|$: 0.049 vs. 0.009, Mann–Whitney U , raw $p = 0.045$), but this did not survive correction for multiple comparisons across the seven factors ($p_{\text{Holm}} = 0.314$). All remaining sex comparisons were non-significant at the raw level ($p > 0.09$).

Age modulation of ablation-induced change in prediction error across psychopathology dimen-

sions. Each panel shows the per-subject change in absolute residual ($\Delta|r_i| = |r_i^{abl}| - |r_i^{base}|$) as a function of age, separately for inter-hemispheric (top row) and intra-hemispheric (bottom row) edge ablation across five psychopathology factors. Each grey dot represents one subject. The regression line is shown in red when the Pearson correlation survives Holm–Bonferroni correction across the five factors within each condition (annotated r-value in red), and in dark grey otherwise. A negative slope indicates that older subjects show a smaller ablation-induced error change — i.e., ablating those edges has less impact on their predictions — while a positive slope indicates the opposite. All panels share the same y-axis range to allow cross-factor comparison.

4. Discussion

Despite consistent evidence that ihFC is altered across psychopathological conditions and reorganizes substantially during childhood and adolescence, few studies have directly contrasted its contribution with that of intra-hemispheric connectivity, particularly across psychopathological dimensions in youth. The present study addressed this gap by training graph neural networks on whole-brain resting-state functional connectivity from the PNC to predict seven dimensions of psychopathology. Edge-class ablations were then used to isolate the respective contribution of inter- and intra-hemispheric edges to each prediction. This approach made it possible to ask not only whether FC carries reliable signal for dimensional psychopathology in youth, but also how that signal is organized along the hemispheric axis, and whether its organization shifts across development.

Graph neural network modeling of whole-brain resting-state FC revealed substantial variability in how reliably the seven psychopathological dimensions could be predicted. *Psychosis*, *depression*, and *obsession/compulsion* yielded reliable signal, while *attention*, *anxiety*, *bipolarity*, and *conduct* showed negligible R^2 . This rank ordering partially aligns with findings from multivariate FC studies conducted in the same cohort. Xia et al. 2018, using four-factor psychopathological dimensions (mood, psychosis, fear, externalizing), reported comparable patterns, with psychosis-spectrum and mood-related dimensions most strongly linked to FC, while externalizing symptoms showed the weakest and least replicable associations. Converging evidence from transdiagnostic dimensional studies in this cohort further supports the neurobiological salience of psychosis and mood dimensions (Cui et al. 2022; Parkes, Satterthwaite, and Bassett 2020), and positive psychosis symptoms have consistently shown the most robust neurobiological signature across imaging modalities in PNC (Wolf et al. 2015; Satterthwaite et al. 2015). Notably, the negligible predictability of *conduct* is consistent with prior PNC findings reporting weak FC associations for externalizing symptoms (Xia et al. 2018). The negligible predictability of *bipolarity*, however, does not straightforwardly follow from this literature: manic symptoms have previously been found to load onto psychosis-spectrum and mood dimensions in PNC factor analyses, which would predict moderate rather than negligible FC signal. No conclusions were drawn from the ablation analyses for these two factors, since the question of which edges a model relies on is ill-posed when the model itself has not learned a generalizable function. Overall, the convergence between predictions derived from a nonlinear deep-learning model and linear sparse canonical correlation analysis (sCCA)-based methods suggests that the predictive ceiling of resting-state FC in this age range is largely captured by relatively simple multivariate models. Further gains will likely require additional modalities, longer scan durations, or richer phenotypic targets rather than increases in model complexity.

Edge-class ablations revealed a dissociation between the contributions of intra-hemispheric and inter-hemispheric connections to psychopathological symptom prediction. This dissociation was

specific to the three reliably predicted dimensions: *psychosis*, *depression*, and *obsession/compulsion*. Removing intra-hemispheric edges produced significant and anatomically specific degradation across these three dimensions, that were consistent across all levels of analysis. In contrast, removing interhemispheric edges yielded inconsistent results across levels of analysis, with comparable group-level performance drops in magnitude, but no consistent subject-level direction. This inconsistency reflects a systematic inversion across the symptom-score distribution: inter-hemispheric ablation degraded predictions for high-scoring participants while, on average, improving them for low-scoring participants. This inversion indicates that the model uses inter-hemispheric edges to encode information that is signed with respect to symptom severity, i.e., the same edges contribute to accurate prediction at one end of the psychosis-spectrum and to inaccurate prediction at the other. One interpretation is that inter- and intra-hemispheric edges encode complementary aspects of core symptoms of the *psychosis*, *depression*, and *obsession/compulsion* dimensions: at elevated symptom levels, intra-hemispheric coupling carries the discriminative signal; at low symptom levels, inter-hemispheric coordination is more informative. This dissociation aligns with evidence that intra- and inter-hemispheric connectivity reflect distinct organizational principles of cortical computation (Tzourio-Mazoyer 2016; Guo et al. 2013). Moreover, these findings also converge with normative-modelling studies documenting that case-control framings systematically average over heterogeneity in clinical brain-behavior relationships (Wolfers et al. 2020; Segal et al. 2023). The present results extend that line of work from individual deviations to the question of which connectivity features are informative for whom: even when group-level predictive features are identified, their direction of contribution can vary systematically across the dimension being predicted.

The pattern of results also points to a more general feature of how predictive signal is distributed in the developing brain. Connectivity that is informative at the group level need not be informative in the same direction for every individual: a connection can carry signal that contributes positively to prediction at one end of a symptom dimension and negatively at the other, producing strong group-level effects with no consistent individual direction. Other connections show the opposite organization, occupying anatomically privileged positions that matter more than arbitrary edges of equivalent size while contributing in heterogeneous directions across participants. Both patterns occurred in the present data, and both would have been hidden — or actively misread — under a single-test framework. More broadly, this suggests that the link between functional connectivity and dimensional psychopathology in youth is not a single feature distributed uniformly across the cohort, but a structured population of contributions that vary with where individuals sit on the symptom dimension being predicted.

Finally, age modulated the ablation effects in a consistent manner: older participants were less affected by inter-hemispheric ablation and more affected by intra-hemispheric ablation, with both effects co-occurring across all studied factors. This pattern aligns with the developmental trajectory described by Tzourio-Mazoyer and Mazoyer (2017), in which inter-hemispheric coordination, relying mostly on callosal pathways, dominates early and gives way to predominantly intra-hemispheric processing as cortical specialization matures. Xia et al. 2018 previously reported that FC linked to mood and psychosis dimensions becomes more prominent with development. The present findings extend this work by showing that development not only reshapes the strength of predictive FC but also its overall hemispheric organization. The fact that age modulation appeared for five factors argues against a single-network or single-symptom mechanism, and in favor of a general developmental reorganization of how psychopathology-relevant signal is distributed across the cortex. Of note, sex effects did not yield any significant findings, consistent with the modest

and inconsistent sex effects reported in FC studies using the PNC (Satterthwaite et al. 2015).

Taken together, these results position the hemispheric axis as an organizing dimension of brain–behavior relationships in youth that has been largely overlooked in transdiagnostic FC research. The same connectivity feature can index different aspects of psychopathology depending on where individuals sit on a symptom dimension and where they sit in development, which complicates the search for stable connectivity markers and argues for interpretation frameworks that resolve signal across severity and age rather than averaging over them.

4.1. Limitations and future directions

Several limitations should be noted. The R^2 values, remain modest in absolute terms; even for psychosis, the model captures a minority of variance, and the present claims apply only to that explained portion. The ablation framework also treats edges independently and does not account for higher-order interactions that may carry additional signal (Battiston et al. 2020). Finally, the cross-sectional design of PNC means that the developmental claims are inferential rather than longitudinal, and replication in longitudinal samples such as ABCD or HCP-D would strengthen the findings of the present study. Building on these results, several directions appear promising. Extending the framework to hypergraph or higher-order models would allow the contribution of multi-edge interactions to be tested directly. Applying the same edge-class ablation logic to longitudinal cohorts would make it possible to track how the inter- to intra-hemispheric shift unfolds within individuals rather than across age groups. More broadly, the dimension-, severity-, and age-dependent structure observed here suggests that brain–behavior models in youth may benefit from interpretation methods designed to capture heterogeneity rather than average it away.

5. Conclusion

Resting-state functional connectivity in PNC carries reliable predictive signal for psychosis, depression and obsession/compulsion psychopathological dimensions, and that signal is anatomically structured along a hemispheric axis. Intra-hemispheric edges support prediction at elevated symptom levels, while inter-hemispheric edges support it at low symptom levels. With age, the relative contribution of inter-hemispheric and intra-hemispheric FC to these dimensions’ prediction shifts from inter- to intra-, tracking a broader developmental reorganization. Overall, our findings suggest that brain–behavior associations in youth are not a single FC signature distributed uniformly across individuals, but a population of dimension-, severity-, and age-dependent signatures that demand interpretation methods sensitive to that heterogeneity.

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Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data and code availability

Data used in this study were obtained from the Philadelphia Neurodevelopmental Cohort (PNC), a collaboration between the Brain Behavior Laboratory at the University of Pennsylvania and the Center for Applied Genomics at the Children’s Hospital of Philadelphia (CHOP). PNC data are publicly available through the NIMH Database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP; accession number phs000607).

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